

SYNERGISTIC ANTI-INFLAMMATORY EFFECTS OF ANDROGRAPHOLIDE AND URSOLIC ACID IN RAW264.7 MACROPHAGES: IMPLICATIONS FOR PSORIASIS THERAPY

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ABSTRACT

Psoriasis is a chronic immune-mediated skin disorder marked by keratinocyte hyperproliferation and elevated pro-inflammatory mediators. The search for effective, safe, and affordable therapies remains a significant challenge. Natural phytochemicals such as andrographolide (AG) and ursolic acid (UA) are known for their anti-inflammatory properties, though their clinical utility is limited by poor oral bioavailability. This study investigated the synergistic anti-inflammatory potential of AG and UA as a novel therapeutic strategy for psoriasis. Using LPS-stimulated RAW264.7 macrophages, we found that AG and UA, individually and in combination, significantly suppressed nitric oxide (NO), IL-1 β , and IL-6 production without cytotoxic effects. Synergy analysis with CompuSyn software revealed a combination index (CI) < 1 for NO inhibition, confirming synergism, with the strongest effect observed at AG (20 μ M) and UA (10 μ M). These findings

indicate that AG and UA act on complementary nodes within the inflammatory signaling network, and their combined use enhances anti-inflammatory efficacy beyond monotherapy. This study supports AG and UA as promising phytochemical-based candidates for managing psoriatic inflammation.

KEYWORDS: Andrographolide; Inflammation; In vitro studies; Synergistic effects; Ursolic acid.

INTRODUCTION

Psoriasis is a chronic, immune-mediated inflammatory disorder of the skin that affects an estimated 125 million individuals worldwide. It is clinically characterized by erythematous, scaly plaques accompanied by epidermal hyperplasia. The onset and exacerbation of psoriasis can be triggered by various factors, including psychological stress, bacterial or viral infections, cutaneous injury, and dysregulation of the immune system.^[1] During the pathogenesis of psoriasis, diverse immune cells become activated and secrete a range of cytokines and chemokines, including interferon- γ (IFN- γ), interleukin (IL)-1 β , IL-6, IL-17, IL-22, IL-23, and tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α). These mediators drive the hyperproliferation and aberrant differentiation of keratinocytes, thereby contributing to the initiation and progression of cutaneous inflammation.^[2,3]

Macrophages are critical immune cells that orchestrate inflammatory responses.^[4] Upon activation, they initiate intracellular signaling cascades that drive the secretion of key pro-inflammatory mediators, including IL-1 β , IL-6, and nitric oxide (NO).^[5,7] NO synthesis is regulated by inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS), while other mediators such as cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) are controlled through transcriptional regulation by nuclear factor- κ B (NF- κ B) and mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) pathways.^[8] Toll-like receptor 4 (TLR4), expressed on macrophages, monocytes, and dendritic cells, plays a pivotal role in innate immune activation. Lipopolysaccharide (LPS), a structural component of Gram-negative bacterial membranes, is specifically recognized by TLR4. Upon LPS binding, TLR4 dimerizes and recruits the adaptor protein MyD88 via its Toll/interleukin-1 receptor (TIR) domain, initiating the MyD88-dependent signaling cascade. This cascade activates transforming growth factor- β -activated kinase 1 (TAK1), which subsequently phosphorylates and activates downstream transcription factors such as NF- κ B and activator protein-1 (AP-1). These transcription factors translocate to the nucleus, inducing the expression of pro-inflammatory genes including iNOS, COX-2, IL-1 β , and IL-6.^[9]

Although biologic therapies targeting TNF- α , IL-17, and IL-23 have transformed the management of psoriasis, they remain costly, require prolonged administration, and pose risks such as infection and immunosuppression.^[10] Conventional synthetic agents, including acitretin, cyclosporine, and methotrexate, are likewise limited by adverse effects such as nephrotoxicity, hepatotoxicity, and other systemic toxicities.^[11] Thus, there is an urgent need to develop novel therapeutic strategies that can provide both long-term efficacy and safety for

the management of psoriasis. Phytochemicals derived from plants are gaining popularity as complementary or alternative treatments for psoriasis due to their affordability, favorable safety profiles, and ability to modulate multiple pathogenic pathways concurrently.^[12]

Andrographolide (AG), a naturally occurring labdane diterpenoid isolated from the leaves of *Andrographis paniculata* (Burm. f.) Nees, has been widely employed in traditional medicine across India, China, and other Asian regions for the treatment of inflammation-related disorders.^[13] AG demonstrates diverse pharmacological properties, including potent anti-inflammatory activity, inhibition of tumor metastasis, and protection against oxidative stress.^[14] Ursolic acid (UA), a naturally occurring pentacyclic triterpenoid, has attracted considerable interest due to its broad pharmacological activities and therapeutic potential. It is abundantly present in various botanical sources, including the leaves of marjoram (*Origanum majorana*), oregano (*Origanum vulgare*), rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*), sage (*Salvia officinalis*), fruit peel of apple (*Malus domestica*), and flowers and leaves of lavender (*Lavandula angustifolia*). UA exhibits diverse biological properties, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, antimicrobial, and anti-diabetic effects.^[15,16] Experimental studies have demonstrated that UA effectively reduces pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α in both in vivo and in vitro models.^[17] Its anti-inflammatory activity is primarily mediated through modulation of the NF- κ B signaling pathway, wherein UA prevents the degradation of I κ B, thereby suppressing NF- κ B activation and reducing the expression of TNF- α , IL-6, and COX-2. In addition, UA inhibits MAPK signaling, particularly the p38 MAPK and JNK pathways, further limiting the production of inflammatory mediators.^[18,19] However, the high hydrophobicity and low oral bioavailability of AG and UA have led to some limitations in their clinical application.^[20,21] Hence, the combination of phytochemicals is one of the strategies to minimize or overcome these limitations, as the synergistic effects can result in equal or greater therapeutic benefits from each drug at lower concentrations.^[22] However, such combinations may also yield antagonistic effects, potentially diminishing therapeutic outcomes as observed with dimeric procyanidin B1 and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA), whose co-administration led to antagonistic effects.^[23] Therefore, it is essential to investigate sensible and efficient compound combination strategies. Although AG and UA have both been found to possess anti-inflammatory potential, the combined effects of these two compounds on inflammation remain unclear.

In this study, the synergistic anti-inflammatory potential of AG and UA in combination was assessed in LPS-stimulated RAW264.7 macrophages by measuring the levels of NO, IL-1 β , and IL-6.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals and reagents

Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) containing L-Glutamine and 4.5 gm/L glucose was procured from MP Biomedicals. Phosphate-buffered saline (Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ free) was purchased from Gibco. Heat-inactivated Foetal Bovine Serum (FBS) and 100X Antibiotic Solution were obtained from HiMedia. Lipopolysaccharide (LPS) from *E. coli* 0111:B4, dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), and MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Andrographolide (AG) (Purity 98%) (Fig. 1B) was purchased from BLD Pharma. Ursolic acid (UA) (Purity 95.15%) (Fig. 1B) was purchased from Yarrow Chem Products. Unless otherwise specified, other reagents were of commercially available analytical grade.

Fig. 1 The chemical structure of (A) andrographolide and (B) ursolic acid.

Cell culture and treatment

The RAW264.7 murine macrophage cell line was purchased from the National Centre for Cell Science (NCCS), Pune, India. Cells were cultured in a complete medium (DMEM supplemented with 10% FBS and 1% antibiotics) at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ humidified incubator. AG and UA were solubilized in DMSO. The final DMSO concentration in cell cultures was less than 0.1%.

Cell viability assay

The cytotoxicity of AG, UA, and their combinations was evaluated using the MTT reduction assay. RAW264.7 macrophages were plated into flat-bottomed 96-well plates at a density of

5×10^4 cells per well and incubated for 24 hours. Cells were pretreated with different concentrations of AG (2.5, 5, 10, 20, 40, 80 μM), UA (1.25, 2.5, 5, 10, 20, 40 μM), or their combination in a ratio of 2:1 for 1 hour, followed by stimulation with LPS (1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) for an additional 24 hours. Then, 20 μL of MTT solution (2.5 mg/mL) was added to each well and incubated at 37°C for 4 hours. The formazan crystals were solubilised with DMSO. Absorbance was then measured at 570 nm using a microplate reader to determine cell viability.

Estimation of nitric oxide production

RAW264.7 macrophages were plated into flat-bottomed 96-well plates at a density of 5×10^4 cells per well and incubated for 24 hours. Cells were pretreated with different concentrations of AG (2.5, 5, 10, 20, 40, 80 μM), UA (1.25, 2.5, 5, 10, 20, 40 μM), or their combination in a ratio of 2:1 for 1 hour, followed by stimulation with LPS (1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) for an additional 24 hours. The supernatant was collected, and nitric oxide (NO) content was determined using the Griess method. Briefly, 50 μL supernatant was mixed with an equal volume of Griess reagent (0.1% N-1-naphthylethylenediamine dihydrochloride and 1% sulphanilamide in 5% phosphoric acid) and incubated for 15 minutes at room temperature in the dark. Subsequently, the absorbance of the reaction mixture was measured at 540 nm using a microplate reader. A standard curve was constructed using sodium nitrite (NaNO_2) as the reference standard to quantify NO concentrations.

Synergy studies using NO assay

The analysis of the synergistic effect of AG and UA on NO levels in RAW264.7 cells was evaluated using CompuSyn software (Version 1.0, ComboSyn Inc., Paramus, USA) with the constant-ratio program. This software was developed by Ting-Chao Chou.^[24] This is a well-established model, which facilitates the characterization of compound interactions. The concentration- NO inhibition rate curves for the GA, UA, individually and their combination at a fixed ratio were generated and subsequently analyzed using the software. The analysis yielded several key outputs, including the combination index–fraction affected (CI-Fa) curve, isobologram plots, median-effect analysis, and relevant statistics about the synergistic/antagonistic interactions. The CI-Fa curve illustrates the relationship between the combination index (CI) and the degree of biological effect. A CI value less than 1 indicates synergism, a value greater than 1 suggests antagonism, and a CI equal to 1 reflects an additive effect.^[25]

In Vitro pro-inflammatory cytokines estimation

RAW264.7 macrophages were plated into flat-bottomed 96-well plates at a density of 5×10^4 cells per well and incubated for 24 hours. Cells were pretreated with AG (20 μM), UA (10 μM), or their combination in a ratio of 2:1 for 1 hour, followed by stimulation with LPS (1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) for an additional 24 hours. The supernatant was collected. The levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β and IL-6 were measured using mouse-specific ELISA kits (R&D Systems, Bio-Techne, Minnesota, USA), according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism version 9. Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). Data were analyzed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of the combination of andrographolide (AG) and ursolic acid (UA) on cell viability

Before evaluating the anti-inflammatory effects of AG and UA on LPS-stimulated RAW264.7 cells, the cytotoxicity of AG (2.5, 5, 10, 20, 40, 80 μM), UA (1.25, 2.5, 5, 10, 20, 40 μM), and their combination in a ratio of 2:1 was assessed in LPS-stimulated RAW264.7 macrophages using the MTT assay. As shown in Fig. 2, the MTT assay revealed no significant changes in macrophage viability following treatment with AG, UA, or their combination. Based on these viability data, the above-mentioned concentrations of AG and UA were chosen for subsequent analysis of the anti-inflammatory potential of the combination.

Fig. 2. Cell viability detected by MTT assays. RAW264.7 cells were plated in 96-well plates at a density of 5×10^4 cells/well and incubated at 37°C for 24 h. The cells were pretreated with AG (2.5, 5, 10, 20, 40, 80 µM) (A), UA (1.25, 2.5, 5, 10, 20, 40 µM) (B), or their combination in a ratio of 2:1 (C) and then stimulated with LPS (1 µg/mL) at 37°C for 24 h. AG, andrographolide; LPS, lipopolysaccharide; UA, ursolic acid. The data are shown as the mean ± SEM of three independent experiments. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way analysis of variance followed by Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test.

Effect of the combination of AG and UA on nitric oxide production in LPS-stimulated RAW264.7 cells

Stimulation of macrophages with LPS triggers the release of nitric oxide (NO), a critical mediator of the inflammatory response. NO production, regulated by inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS), plays a role in psoriatic inflammation by influencing keratinocyte proliferation, differentiation, and disease progression.^[26] Hence, the inhibition of NO production is considered a promising strategy for mitigating inflammatory reactions. Therefore, the effect of AG and UA on NO levels in LPS-stimulated RAW264.7 cells was evaluated.

Fig. 3. Percentage inhibition of NO production by AG, UA, and their combination in LPS-stimulated RAW264.7 cells. Cells (5×10^4 cells/well) were pretreated with the indicated concentrations of AG (A), UA (B), or their combination in a ratio of 2:1 (C) for 1 h, followed by stimulation with LPS (1 µg/mL) for 24 h. NO levels in the culture supernatant were quantified using the Griess reagent. Data are shown as mean \pm SEM of three independent experiments. AG, andrographolide; LPS, lipopolysaccharide; NO, nitric oxide; UA, ursolic acid. Data were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance followed by Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test. ##### $p < 0.0001$ vs untreated cells; * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, **** $p < 0.0001$ vs LPS group; \$ $p < 0.05$, \$\$ $p < 0.01$, \$\$\$ $p < 0.0001$ vs AG + UA group.

As shown in Fig. 3, the level of the secreted inflammatory mediator NO in RAW264.7 cells was extremely low in the absence of LPS stimulation. LPS stimulation significantly increased NO production in RAW264.7 cells, which was dose-dependently inhibited by pretreatment with AG and UA (Fig. 3, A and B). Moreover, the combination of AG and UA at a 2:1 ratio had a more significant inhibitory effect on the NO than AG or UA alone.

Evaluation of the synergistic anti-inflammatory effects of AG in combination with UA

Combination index (CI) and isobologram analyses were carried out using CompuSyn Software (Version 1.0) to determine the synergistic interaction between AG and UA in modulating LPS-induced NO production. These analyses were performed using NO inhibition data obtained from treatments with AG and UA, both individually and in combination. Fig. 4A shows the isobologram analysis for the combination of AG and UA.

The individual doses of AG and UA to achieve 90% inhibition ($F_a = 0.9$; green line) were calculated and plotted on the y- and x-axes by the CompuSyn software 1.0. AG and UA doses in combinations that achieved the same F_a were also plotted to indicate synergism (the

plotted point is below the line) and antagonism (the plotted point is above the line). As shown in Fig. 4A, the plotted value for 90% inhibition ($F_a = 0.9$; green triangle) fell below the line, demonstrating a synergistic anti-inflammatory interaction between AG and UA.

The combination index (CI) provides a quantitative measure of drug interactions, indicating synergism, additivity, or antagonism for a given endpoint. Specifically, CI values < 1 denote synergism, CI = 1 reflects an additive effect, and CI > 1 indicates antagonism, with lower CI values corresponding to stronger synergistic interactions. As shown in Fig. 4B, the CI values for AG and UA (molar ratio 2:1) ranged from 0.76 to 0.89. The combination of AG (20 μM) and UA (10 μM) yielded the lowest CI value (0.76), demonstrating the strongest synergistic effect. Furthermore, the F_a -Dose curves revealed that, at equivalent doses, NO levels (F_a values) in the combination group were consistently lower than those in the AG or UA groups alone, confirming that the combined treatment exerted a more potent anti-inflammatory effect (Fig. 4C).

Based on these findings, the combination of AG (20 μM) and UA (10 μM) was selected for subsequent experiments. The effect of AG and UA, individually or in combination, using the aforementioned dose on LPS-induced pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β and IL-6) was further evaluated to understand the synergistic anti-inflammatory effect of AG and UA.

Fig. 4. (A) Isobologram curves for AG, UA, and their combination on inhibition of NO production in LPS-stimulated RAW264.7 cells. (B) Combination index (CI) for AG and/or UA on inhibition of NO production in LPS-stimulated RAW264.7 cells. The black line is the reference line, where the CI value is equal to 1. (C) Fa-Dose curve of AG, UA, and their combination. AG, andrographolide; UA, ursolic acid. Data processing was done using CompuSyn Software (Version 1.0).

Effects of the combination of AG with UA on IL-1 β and IL-6 production in LPS-stimulated RAW264.7 cells

Elevated levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 β and IL-6 are closely linked to the immunopathogenesis of psoriasis, with their expression regulated through the NF- κ B and MAPK signaling pathways.^[27] Consequently, suppressing cytokine production is regarded as an effective strategy for alleviating inflammation-related disorders. To evaluate the anti-inflammatory potential of AG, UA, and their combination, IL-1 β and IL-6 levels were measured in LPS-stimulated RAW264.7 macrophages using ELISA. As shown in Fig. 5, LPS stimulation significantly increased IL-1 β and IL-6 expression, whereas treatment with AG, UA, or their combination significantly reduced cytokine levels, demonstrating strong anti-inflammatory activity. AG reduced IL-1 β and IL-6 expression by 27% and 30%, respectively. UA reduced IL-1 β and IL-6 expression by 19% and 22%, respectively. While the combination of AG and UA produced the most pronounced effect, lowering IL-1 β by 35% and IL-6 by 39%. These findings suggest that the combination of AG and UA exerts a more pronounced inhibitory effect on IL-1 β and IL-6 expression than either agent alone. The enhanced suppression of IL-1 β and IL-6 by the combination treatment highlights the potential therapeutic advantage of using AG and UA together rather than as single agents. This synergistic activity may be attributed to complementary mechanisms of action, where AG and UA target distinct pathways involved in cytokine regulation.

Fig. 5. Effects of AG, UA and their combination on pro-inflammatory cytokines (A) IL-1 β and (B) IL-6 in LPS-stimulated RAW264.7 cells. Cells (5×10^4 cells/well) were plated in 96-well plates and then pretreated with the AG (20 μ M) and/or UA (10 μ M) for 1 hour, followed by LPS stimulation for 24 hours without removing the compounds. IL-1 β and IL-6 production in the culture media was determined using an ELISA kit. The data are shown as the mean \pm SEM (n = 3). AG, andrographolide; IL-1 β , interleukin-1 β ; IL-6, interleukin-6; LPS, lipopolysaccharide; UA, ursolic acid. Data were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance followed by Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test. ##### p < 0.0001 vs untreated cells; ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001, **** p < 0.0001 vs LPS group; \$ p < 0.05 vs AG + UA group.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that the AG in combination with UA exerts synergistic anti-inflammatory effects in LPS-stimulated RAW264.7 macrophages. These findings suggest that the combination of AG and UA may be an effective approach for the treatment of psoriatic inflammation.

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